

**THE DEVELOPMENT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IS THE
BASIS OF THE MODERN ECONOMY**

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Abstract. The development of artificial intelligence (AI) has become the foundation of the modern economy. AI technologies, such as machine learning and deep learning, have revolutionized various industries, including finance, healthcare, manufacturing, and transportation. This annotation explores how AI is shaping the modern economy by enhancing productivity, enabling data-driven decision-making, and fostering innovation. It examines the benefits and challenges associated with AI adoption, highlighting its potential to drive economic growth, create new job opportunities, and transform business models. Additionally, the annotation discusses the ethical and regulatory considerations that arise with AI implementation, emphasizing the importance of responsible AI development and deployment. Overall, it underscores the significant role of AI in shaping the future of the economy and encourages further exploration of its potential impacts and implications.

Key words: Artificial intelligence, learning algorithms, healthcare, industry

I. Introduction

It should be noted that today the most important issue is the development of a digital economy based on artificial intelligence. In this regard, developing countries are trying to move towards a digital economy. The digital economy cannot be imagined

without artificial intelligence, so we must first study artificial intelligence and its evolution. Artificial intelligence allows computers to learn from experience, adapt to parameters presented to them, and perform tasks that were previously only performed by humans. The term "artificial intelligence" appeared in 1956, but the real popularity of AI technology has reached only today against the backdrop of increasing data volumes, improving algorithms, optimizing computing power and data storage facilities.

The first research in the field of AI, which started in the 50s of the last century, was aimed at solving problems and developing symbolic computing systems. In the 60s, this direction attracted the interest of the US Department of Defense: the US military began to train computers to imitate human mental activity. For example, the US Department of Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) carried out a number of projects in the 70s to create virtual street maps. And DARPA managed to create intelligent personal assistants in 2003, long before there were Siri, Alexa and Cortana.

These works became the basis for the principles of automation and formal logic of reasoning that are used in modern computers, in particular, in decision support systems and smart search engines designed to complement and enhance human capabilities [7,9].

Although AI is often depicted in science fiction films and novels as humanoid robots taking over the world, at this stage in the development of AI technology, AI is not at all scary and not nearly as smart. On the contrary, the development of artificial intelligence allows these technologies to bring real benefits in all sectors of the economy.

II. Artificial intelligence technology

Artificial intelligence allows existing products to become intelligent. Artificial intelligence technology is rarely used as a standalone application. AI functionality is integrated into existing products, allowing you to enhance them in the same way that Siri was added to next-generation Apple devices. When combined with big data,

automation, communication platforms, bots and smart computers can enhance a wide range of home and office technologies, from security data analysis to investment analysis tools.

As a result of progressive learning algorithms, AI is adapting, allowing more to be programmed from data. AI defines data structures and patterns that allow the algorithm to learn a certain skill: the algorithm is converted into a classifier or predictor. As a result, the algorithm can learn to offer relevant products on the Internet, applying the same principle as when mastering chess. At the same time, the models are adapted as new data become available. Backpropagation is a technique that corrects the model by learning new data if the original answer turns out to be wrong.

Artificial intelligence allows you to get the most out of your data. With the advent of self-learning algorithms, the data itself becomes an object of intellectual property. Answers in data; all you have to do is find them with the help of artificial intelligence technology. Data that matters more than ever can provide a competitive advantage. When using the same technologies in a competitive environment, the one with the most accurate data wins [1,6].

Artificial intelligence is in high demand across all industries, especially in question and answer systems for legal aid, patent search, risk communication, and medical research. Other uses for AI are listed below:

Healthcare: Artificial intelligence can be used in personalized medicine and X-ray decoding. Personal care assistants can help users remember to take their medications, exercise or change their diet.

Industry: AI can analyze site IoT data from connected equipment and predict usage and demand using repeating networks, a type of deep learning network that works with sequential data.

Retail: Artificial intelligence helps shoppers shop online by providing personalized recommendations and allowing merchants to communicate with shoppers about their purchases. Artificial intelligence can also help with inventory management and product placement [4,5].

Sports: Coaches are provided with camera and sensor reports on how best to organize the game, including player placement and strategy optimization.

Summing up, we can say that the purpose of artificial intelligence is to ensure the correct operation of software products that are able to analyze and interpret input data. Artificial intelligence is a tool that provides a more intuitive human-computer interaction and helps make decisions in specific tasks. AI is not and will not be a viable human replacement for the foreseeable future.

III. Applications of artificial intelligence (AI) in the modern economy

The development of artificial intelligence (AI) in the modern economy has led to a wide range of applications across various sectors. These applications are transforming industries, enhancing productivity, and driving economic growth.

One prominent application of AI in the modern economy is in the field of healthcare. AI-powered systems can analyze medical data, assist in diagnosing diseases, and support treatment planning. Medical professionals can leverage AI algorithms to improve patient outcomes, optimize resource allocation, and enhance the overall efficiency of healthcare delivery [10,11].

Fig 1. Main applications of AI

In the financial sector, AI is revolutionizing processes such as fraud detection, risk assessment, and algorithmic trading. Advanced AI models can analyze vast amounts of financial data in real-time, enabling more accurate predictions and smarter investment decisions. AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants are also being employed to enhance customer service and improve the user experience in the banking and financial services industry.

Fig 2. Applications of AI In the financial sector

AI has also found applications in manufacturing and supply chain management. Intelligent robots and automation systems powered by AI algorithms can optimize production processes, reduce errors, and enhance operational efficiency. AI-driven predictive analytics can help businesses optimize inventory management, anticipate demand fluctuations, and streamline logistics operations [3].

Furthermore, AI is transforming the transportation and logistics industry. Self-driving vehicles, guided by AI algorithms, have the potential to improve road safety, reduce congestion, and enhance overall transportation efficiency. AI-powered routing and scheduling systems are being employed to optimize delivery routes and reduce transportation costs.

In the retail sector, AI is being used to personalize customer experiences, improve inventory management, and optimize pricing strategies. AI algorithms can analyze

customer data to provide personalized product recommendations, optimize stock levels, and dynamically adjust prices based on demand and market trends [14,15].

IV. Conclusion

The development of artificial intelligence (AI) serves as the foundation of the modern economy. In today's world, AI is penetrating into an increasing number of industries and exerting a significant influence on economic activities. Artificial intelligence enhances productivity and efficiency across various economic sectors. Through the automation and optimization of processes using AI, costs can be reduced, task completion time can be shortened, and the quality of products and services can be improved.

Data-driven decision-making is becoming an increasingly vital aspect of the modern economy, and AI plays a key role in this process. Machine learning and deep learning algorithms have the capability to analyze vast amounts of data, uncovering hidden patterns and relationships, thereby aiding businesses in making more precise and informed decisions.

The advancement of AI also stimulates innovation in the economy. New technological solutions based on AI enable the creation of novel products and services, improvement of existing processes, and the opening of new markets. This contributes to economic growth and the generation of new job opportunities.

However, with the development of AI, challenges and issues arise. Matters related to the ethical aspects of AI usage, data confidentiality, and security demand serious attention and the development of appropriate norms and regulations.

Overall, the development of artificial intelligence is an integral part of the modern economy. AI provides businesses and individuals with new possibilities, enhances efficiency, and fosters innovation. Understanding and utilizing AI are becoming increasingly crucial for successful development and prosperity in the contemporary economic landscape.

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